

VOCABULARY BUILDING STRATEGIES AND PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

MICHAEL B. ROSALES¹

ANNA LIZA P. DEL ROSARIO²

michael.rosales001@deped.gov.ph¹

annaliza.delrosario@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-8883-8128¹

0000-0002-2034-632X²

San Isidro National High School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Based from the various results of the different international test (PISA, 2019) that the Philippines was one of the participants, it is very alarming that the country got the second lowest rank in terms of Mathematics and Science literacy. To address this scenario, the study tries to make an improvement on the basic requirement for students in understanding word problems related to Mathematics which is vocabulary building. This study introduced five vocabulary building strategies included in the supplemental learning materials provided to the students which is conducive to increasing the problem-solving skills of thirty-two (32) Grade 7 students in San Isidro National High School of the School Year 2020-2021. An experimental research design was used and utilized by a pretest and posttest that led into the following scenario. The result showed a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the learners which implies that the use of supplemental learning materials focusing on the improvement of students' vocabulary building helped students in achieving a better result. This indicates that from "Beginning" and "Developing" stage in their level of solving math-related problems, the students were able to reach at least from "Approaching Proficient" to "Advanced" level of performance. With this implication, it is highly recommended for teachers to use different vocabulary building strategies not only to enhance the skills of the learners in problem solving but also to familiarize them to some uncommon terminologies and concepts.

Keywords: Vocabulary building strategies, Problem solving skills